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Effects of Frequent Domestic Conflicts and Violence on Social Behaviour and Cognitive Development of School Children in Kwazo Academy Jega, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on social behavior and cognitive development of school children in Kwazo academy, Jega Kebbi State, Nigeria. Three objectives and research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Fifty five (55) pre-school children and seventy three (73) school age children out of the total population of 357 were identified as subject for the study. Observation, oral interview and continuous assessment record were used to assess their social behavior and cognitive development. The findings revealed among others that there was 39.0% prevalence of frequent domestic conflict and violence in the study area and there was significant effect of these tendencies on the social behaviours and cognitive development of both pre-school and school age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega. Based on these findings, it was recommended that parents and grown up family members should be enlightened on the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on their children so as to minimize the rate of the prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in homes and its negative effects on the children.

Keywords: Domestic conflicts, Social behavior, violence, Cognitive development and Academy

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Introduction

The family, the basic unit of social life, forms the essential link between individuals and society. It is a system of accepted norms and procedures for fulfilling human needs (Amagon & Wakjissa, 2001). Families, whether nuclear, polygamous, or extended, provide for the rearing of children and meet various human needs (Adeniyi, 2003). Extended families, while geographically dispersed, come together in villages, potentially leading to conflicts (Anyakoha & Eluwa, 2008).

Domestic conflict, defined as misunderstandings among family members, is common. Domestic violence, an intentional use of physical abuse causing pain or injury, exacerbates these conflicts (Espion, 2008; Gilchrist & Graham, 2009). It includes behaviors like throwing objects, pushing, hitting, and threatening, perpetrated by one partner against another in an intimate relationship or parent-child context (Adeniyi, 2003). These conflicts manifest as anxiety, depression, isolation, and communication gaps (Cumming, 2006).

Children are profoundly affected by domestic violence, even if they are not direct victims. Parents often underestimate their children's awareness of these events (Laura, 2011). Children hear the fighting, see the injuries, and experience the emotional pain, impacting their cognitive growth (Laura, 2011).

Social behavior, conduct accepted within a society, is shaped within the family (Carpenter & Stacks, 2009). Children exposed to violence exhibit psychosomatic illnesses, depression, bed-wetting, and suicidal tendencies Adeniyi, E. I. (2003). Children aged one to six show internalizing and externalizing behavior problems, including depression, anxiety, hyperactivity, sleep disturbances, and poor concentration (Carpenter & Stacks, 2009).

Cognitive development, encompassing learning and problem-solving abilities, is influenced by observation and imitation (Anderson & Bushman in Reisberg, 2004). Children imitate behaviors they witness, and violence exposure affects their development (Anderson & Bushman in Reisberg, 2004). Pre-school and school-age children are particularly vulnerable to the effects of parental conflicts (Richard, 2011). They may act out, feel sad, become aggressive, or exhibit behavioral problems like frequent illness and isolation (Abraham, 2004).

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Primary school children (age, six to twelve) are in a critical cognitive development stage, characterized by intellectual curiosity and performance (Kitsman, 2007). Erickson, as cited in Snowman, McCown, & Biehler (2009), observed that children develop a sense of industry through achievement. However, domestic conflicts and violence can lead to

Inferiority complexes, impaired thinking, and poor problem-solving skills (Alexander, 2004).

Statement of the Research Problem

It is generally observed by the researchers that young children between the ages of three to ten years are generally falling victim to circumstances that happen among the family members. Most of their learning behaviour is through the daily practice of what they see happening around them. Children exposed to frequent domestic conflicts and violence do not have the foundations of safety and security that is normally provided by the family. As a result of that, the children experience desensitized to aggressive behaviour, poor anger management and problem solving skills and learn to engage in exploitative relationships (Adeniyi, 2003).

The researchers has observed and interacted with some parents, nursery and primary school teachers and care-givers that some pre-school and school-age children in nursery and primary school in the Kwazo academy, Jega develop a range of problems in school which include psychosomatic complaints, such as headaches or abdominal pain, as well as poor school performances are part of the general problems of children that come from conflict dominated homes. It has also been observed that these children do not have many friends or participate in outdoor activities; they do not have a sense of self-esteem and confidence. One of the researcher was also opportune to observe a role played by some children during an outdoor games in a primary school in Kebbi state and one of the pupils was asked to act as a father. He quickly declined to pick that role on the excuse that his father is very abusive and always fighting the mother. The statement by this pupil stated above caught the attention of the researchers and views of other researchers in relation to this topic has prompted this study to investigate the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on social behaviour and cognitive development of pre-school and school age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega local government Kebbi state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

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1. Ascertain the prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
2. Identify the social behaviour of children from families with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
3. Assess the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of school-age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
2. There is no significant difference in social behaviour of pre-school children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
3. There is no significant effect of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of school-age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Methodology

Research Design

The research design for this study was survey research design. This design involves the gathering of data from accessible population at a particular period. According to Olayiwola (2007) survey research involves a clear definition of the problem, collection of relevant and adequate data, careful analysis and interpretation of the finding. A survey research design therefore was selected because it allows for the selection of sample from the total population having traits and characteristics of interest.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised children in Nursery and Primary Schools in Kwazo Academy, Jega during 2024/2025 academic session in Kebbi state.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A sample of 128 nursery and primary school children were selected from the study area. The researchers used random sampling to select the target classes for the study and proportionate sampling methods to select the respondents. This is because the number of pupils in the target classes of study is not uniform.

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Instrument for Data Collection

The instruments used for this study were oral interview, observation and children's continuous assessment records. The instrument is divided into four (4) sections. Section A is the bio-data of the respondents while Section B consist of 10 questionnaire items which were designed using the adapted assessment pattern of family violence by Boney and Sugar Man in Rathus and Silver (2003). This is used to interview the children in order to ascertain the prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega. Section C also consist of 10 items which served as a guide line in observing and identifying the social behaviours of children from families with frequent domestic conflicts and violence. To structure the observation guide the researchers adapted the social behaviour patterns of children as stated by Hurlock (2001). Section D also consists of 10 interview questions respectively and to assess the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of pre-school and school age children, the questions were design using the nursery and primary school syllabus.

Validity of the Instrument

The items on the instruments for this study were given to experts in the field of Home Economics in the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Adamu Augie College of Education Argungu to vet the content validity. The interview and observation items were also vetted by an expert in the field of family and child development to ensure that the instrument measures accurately what it is intended to measure. The corrected questionnaires were used for pilot study to ascertain the reliability coefficient of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The data collected from the pilot study was analyzed for the purpose of reliability coefficient. Consequently the Cronbach reliability level of .806 was obtained for the nursery school section and 0.919 was obtained for the primary school section. According to Spiegel and Stevens (1999) an instrument is considered reliable if its reliability coefficient lies between zero (0) and one (1), and that the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to zero the less reliable is the instrument and the closer it is to one the more reliable is the instrument.

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Procedure for Data Collection

The researchers through the help of the headmaster, class teachers and care givers who were trained by the researchers interviewed the 128 children using the questionnaire items in section B. the researchers with the help of the class teachers during the interview selected the children one after the other who were identify as the subjects for the study. These children were used to answer the questions in section C and D, respectively. The researchers used direct and indirect method of observation to assess the social behaviour patterns of the children; this is to minimize the tendency of the children faking their behaviour. This was done using the guidelines in section C. The questionnaires in section D were administered to the children using oral test. The researchers graded them using their continuous assessment records and students coding sheets based on their performance and it lasted for six (6) weeks.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using inferential statistics. All the null-hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. This is in line with Aloysin and John (2000) who explained that t-test is the most appropriate statistical tool to find out differences and effects among variables.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega*

Table 1: One sample t-test of Prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Variables	N	Mean	t-Cal	t-Crit	DF	P
Prevalence	56	1.0546	2.081	1.96	54	0.000

Source: Fieldwork 2025

$t(127) 1.96, P < 0.05$

The test in Table 1, revealed that 56 children out of the total sample of 128 were identified from pre-school children and school age children. The observed t-calculated is 2.081 which is greater than the t-critical of 1.96 at the 54 degree of freedom and the probability level of significance observed in the test is 0.000 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was significant prevalence of frequent domestic

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conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant difference in social behaviours of pre-school children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega.*

Table 2: One sample t-test on social behaviours of pre-school children in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Variables	N	Mean	t-Cal	t-Crit	DF	P
Pre-school age children	53	-.25455	-1.308	2.01	51	0.000

Source: Fieldwork 2025

$t(54) 2.01, P < 0.05$

The test in Table 2, revealed that 53 students were identified for pre-school children. The observed t-calculated is -1.308 which is less than the t-critical of 2.01 at the 51 degree of freedom and the probability level of significance observed in the test is 0.000 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was significant difference in the behaviours of the pre-school children. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in social behaviours of pre-school children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 3: *There is no significant effect of frequent domestic conflicts and violent on cognitive development of school age children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega.*

Table 3: One sample t-test on effect of cognitive development of school age children in Kwazo academy, Jega

Variables	N	Mean	t-Cal	t-Crit	DF	P
school age children	71	-.24364	-2.281	2.01	69	0.000

Source: Fieldwork 2025

$t(72) 2.01, P < 0.05$

The test in Table 3, revealed that 710 school age children were identified. The observed t-calculated is -2.281 which is less than the t-critical of 2.01 at the 69 degree of freedom and the probability level of significance observed in the test is

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0.000 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was significant difference in cognitive development of school age children. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant effect of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of school age children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed in the test of null hypothesis that the probability level of significance observed in the test was 0.00 ($P < 0.05$). This shows that frequent domestic conflicts and violence had effects on school age children. The finding is in line with Laura (2011) who states that in many homes where domestic violence occurs, the parents are under the misconception that their children are unaware of the violence even if it has taken place in close proximity to the children. They may not witness the actual violence but they do hear the fighting, hear the screams and see the injuries. These children are also traumatized by the parent's emotional pain and suffering after the violence had taken place and this directly and indirectly have devastating effects on their cognitive growth. Witnessing domestic violence can lead children to develop an array of age-dependent and negative effect. Cumming, (2005) stated that children who witness violence in the home and children who are abused may display many similar psychological effects.

The school age children have significant difference in their cognitive development. This was further confirmed with Bandura in John (2008) who emphasizes that cognitive development and social behavior have important links with environment. His research program focused mainly on observational learning also called imitation or modeling, which is learning that occurs through observing what others do; for example, a young child might observe his parents yelling at each other in anger or treating other people with hostility, with his peers, the child may later act very aggressively. Bandura proposed that children cognitively represent the behavior of others and then sometimes adopted this behavior themselves. Elizabeth (2011) opines that when parents are in conflict situations, pre-school and school age children are seriously affected, while many parents think that they are keeping the conflict away from their children, the children notice tension in the home and it has a profound effect on their social behavior and cognitive development. Some children respond to parental conflict by acting out, violence behavior, increased anger and turning inward, isolation from parents and friends, while some may have trouble

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thinking, impaired thinking, abstract reasoning, poor problem solving skills and their memories affected.

Finally, the frequent domestic conflicts and violence on social behavior and cognitive development have effect on school age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega thereby affecting their behaviours, socially and cognitively.

Conclusion

From the findings it was discovered that prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in homes can be seen displayed among school age children. It could be deduced that frequent domestic conflicts and violence of homes in Kwazo academy, Jega has influence on a lot of children that stirred up violence in them right from their childhood. Parents should be aware of the fact that their actions can affect their children's future and violent act in the presence and around their children can affect their cognitive development.

Recommendations

1. Parents and grown up members of the family should be enlightened on the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence so as to minimize the rate of negative effect on the children's social behaviour and cognitive development.
2. Guidance and counseling unit should be built into the nursery and primary schools to curb and ameliorate whatever trauma the children of school age children had due to frequent domestic conflicts and violence.
3. Parents should be enlightened on their roles as good model to their children because children learn faster at their tender ages and also believe that what their parents do is the ultimate.

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